

Challenges and considerations for analysing multiple long-term conditions: First report of the MLTC Research Statistical Methods and Clinical Communities of Practice

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Introduction

Multiple long-term conditions (MLTCs), previously referred to as multimorbidity¹, are defined as the co-occurrence of two or more health conditions exist together in a person. MLTC is increasing globally and across the life course, with a higher prevalence among older individuals, ethnic minority groups, and people experiencing socioeconomic deprivation². This rise is multifactorial, partly due to increased diagnostic efforts, but also reflects significant healthcare improvements, such as cardiovascular interventions leading to better survival outcomes. The NIHR (National Institute for Health and Care Research) estimates that 14 million people in England are living with MLTCs, with these individuals accounting for over half of primary and secondary healthcare costs in the National Health Service (NHS)³. With an ageing population and improved treatments for previously fatal illnesses, this number is likely to grow further.

Research challenges include developing an operational definition of MLTCs, determining the best methods to quantify MLTCs across age, sex, ethnic groups, and socioeconomic status, and identifying patterns of MLTCs, including distinguishing random from non-random disease clusters. Understanding

the underlying mechanisms, such as the roles of socioeconomic drivers, biological risk factors, and the impact of medications and polypharmacy, is also essential.

In 2015, the UK Chief Medical Officer and the Academy of Medical Sciences initiated discussions on the challenges of MLTCs, which led to its identification as a key research priority by UK funders, including the Medical Research Council (MRC) and NIHR. Subsequently, the NIHR conducted three workshops involving carers of children with complex care needs, young and working-age people, older individuals with MLTCs, and carers, to ensure research policies aligned with the priorities of people living with MLTC⁴. In 2020-2021, NIHR funded seven national research collaborations (£23 million) to investigate MLTCs using artificial intelligence, and in 2021 the MRC funded six national research collaboratives (£18 million) to study MLTCs. Additionally, the MRC funded three Communities of Practice (CoPs) to facilitate collaboration across MRC research groups: 1) MLTC CoP in Clinical Context and Pathways, 2) Early Career Researcher Training on Best Practice in Patient and Public Involvement with Diverse Populations CoP, and 3) the Statistical Methods in MLTC Research CoP. A fourth Qualitative Methods for MLTC research CoP was later incorporated into the MRC portfolio.

This paper presents findings from the Statistical Methods and Clinical Context CoPs. The Statistical Methods in MLTC Research CoP hosted a workshop in Leicester in January 2023, bringing together 12 representatives from five MRC-funded MLTC collaboratives and the AIM RSF (Artificial Intelligence in MLTC Research Support Facility). The workshop aimed to establish best practices for defining MLTCs for analytical purposes. The Clinical Context and Pathways CoP, with support from the three other CoPs, hosted a workshop at the Society for Academic Primary Care conference in Brighton in July 2023, where attendees were invited to identify barriers to MLTC research and potential solutions. This manuscript summarises discussions from these workshops and highlights key challenges for future MLTC research.

Defining MLTC

The widely accepted definition of MLTCs is the '*co-occurrence of multiple chronic or acute diseases and medical conditions within one person*'⁵.

Diseases *without a shared cause* co-occur at random, at rates consistent with their individual frequencies. Characterising the number and types of these conditions is important for planning service provision, while longitudinal follow-up can help estimate the risks of adverse outcomes. Conversely, diseases that *share common causes* co-occur more frequently than would be expected by chance, assuming their independence. Understanding these causes is essential for identifying shared mechanisms and risk factors.

Non-random clustering of diseases can arise from various factors, including common environmental exposures (e.g. smoking leading to both coagulation and DNA damage, which in turn can cause stroke and cancer), one condition causing another (e.g. atrial fibrillation leading to ischaemic stroke), treatment of one condition causing another (e.g. anticoagulation for pulmonary embolism resulting in subdural haemorrhage), or shared biological mechanisms (e.g. telomere shortening and diseases such as pulmonary fibrosis and liver cirrhosis).

However, discussions from both workshops identified several limitations in this definition. These include the need to consider the impacts of MLTCs across the life course, measures of disease severity, issues related to treatment and diagnostic validity and practicalities in defining MLTCs using routinely collected health data.

Definition of MLTCs in research for analytical purposes

The established definition of MLTCs has limitations in characterising mechanisms or changes in prevalence over time. This general definition may not suit all MLTC studies, where more specific definitions are required to address specific research questions. For example, research on MLTC may focus on particular populations, subsets of conditions, healthcare settings, mechanistic pathways or conditions with shared treatments, and it is crucial to choose an MLTC definition that aligns with the research aims.

Researchers must first decide which conditions to include when defining individuals with MLTCs. If the research focuses on risk factors or biological mechanisms, a broader definition might be more appropriate, ensuring all cases are included to maximise the study's power. However, for estimating MLTC prevalence, a stricter definition might be necessary.

Studying rare conditions can be challenging due to small sample sizes reducing the power of analyses. It is also difficult to study rare conditions in datasets without breaking anonymity of the individuals with those conditions. For this reason, MLTC studies often focus on conditions common in the population, such as those with a prevalence greater than 1%. In this instance, it is important to consider the population in which prevalence is calculated, as some conditions may be more common in specific sex, age, or ethnicity groups, and therefore further stratification should be considered.

Clinical consensus can help refine conditions of interest in specific research contexts. One method to achieve this is the Delphi study, which uses iterative rounds of questionnaires to gain consensus⁶. For example, a Delphi study, involving 175 professional and public participants (predominantly from high-income countries) by Ho et al⁷ reached a consensus on a list of 24 conditions that should always be included in MLTC definitions, with an additional 35 conditions that could be included unless there is reason not to. Similarly, Delphi studies are suitable for more specific MLTC research questions. For example, Massen et al⁸ used a Delphi approach to identify conditions relevant to fibrotic multimorbidity.

The impact of a condition may extend beyond the duration of clinical diagnosis. For example, treatment effects can persist for years, such as osteoporotic fractures following steroid treatment. Similarly, cardiovascular disease may develop as a late complication of adolescent malignancy or its treatment. Acute events, like myocardial infarction and hip fracture, can arise from antecedent risk factors (e.g., hypertension or osteoporosis) and may lead to long-term outcomes, such as heart failure or venous thromboembolic disease. For mechanistic research and depending on the specific research question, it is justifiable to extend the MLTC definition to the *occurrence of two or more conditions over the life course*⁹. However, for prevalence estimates, the concurrent co-existing conditions remains the most appropriate definition. This raises important nuance when defining conditions as *acute* versus *chronic*, with MLTC literature typically categorising chronic diseases as those that develop slowly and cannot be cured but can be managed with treatment.

The different approaches to tailoring a definition for specific research aims are evident in the UK MLTC research portfolio, particularly in the six MRC-funded Research Collaboratives which all used different MLTC definitions to answer different research questions:

- The GEMINI research collaborative focussed on chronic, common, heritable conditions in individuals aged ≥ 65 years, studying genetic and observed associations using large-scale clinical and genetic data.

- ADMISSION applied a similar case definition by investigating only common conditions, though restricted to a particular clinical setting, namely investigating individuals with two or more MLTCs who have been admitted to hospital.
- MMTRC separated conditions that co-occurred in line with their individual frequencies from those that co-occurred more frequently than expected from their individual frequencies.
- LINC focussed on specific common, high-burden diseases (internalising disorders and cardiometabolic conditions) and investigated these across the life course. Where necessary, precursors of these diseases were used when analysing childhood and adolescent cohorts.
- MuM-PreDiCT focussed on MLTCs in a specific group of individuals, namely pregnant women.
- DEMISTIFI investigated conditions with shared mechanistic outcomes, focusing on all conditions related to fibrosis, regardless of prevalence.

Ultimately, before defining MLTC in research, it is essential to consider the specificity of the definition to be used. However, the final definition may be determined by the available data for operationalising the definition and the statistical methods employed.

Sources of data for MLTC research

Routinely collected healthcare data provides population-representative information, though the completeness of this data may vary depending on the healthcare system. In the UK, the NHS is free at the point of access and allows for population-representative research using routine healthcare data from both primary and secondary care across the life course. Data derived from the NHS, without exclusions applied, is inclusive of MLTC, polypharmacy, frailty, physical disability, access, and socioeconomic factors—elements that can pose barriers to research participation and lead to bias. In the UK, CPRD (Clinical Practice Research Datalink) offers access to de-identified primary care data for 60 million patients¹⁰. Electronic health records can also be accessed through OpenSAFELY, SAIL (Secure Anonymised Information Linkage) Databank, THIN (The Health Improvement Network), DataLoch, QResearch, and NHS Digital Platforms¹¹⁻¹³. It is possible to link between electronic healthcare records and other data sources such as Hospital Episode Statistics (HES) and death registration data to gain greater insight into conditions and events recorded across healthcare settings where triangulation of data increases data completeness. Specific registries or audit programmes also exist for routine data collection, such as the National Congenital Anomaly and Rare Disease Registration Service (NCARDRS), the National Cancer Registration and Analysis Services (NCRAS), and the National Institute for Cardiovascular Outcomes Research (NICOR)¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

Biobanks are studies that collect a wide range of measures, conditions, and biological samples that may not be available in electronic health records from cohorts of individuals. UK Biobank¹⁷, for instance, recruited 500,000 participants completing questionnaires (including about health and environmental exposures), physical tests (e.g. blood pressure, spirometry, bone density), imaging (in a subset of participants), and provided biological samples for biomarkers (e.g. cholesterol) and omics (e.g. genetics and proteomics). Data linkage with hospital episode statistics, primary care data (for a subset of individuals) and death records has further enriched the resource. National biobanks, such as FinnGen¹⁸ in Finland (n=500,000), China Kadoorie Biobank¹⁹ (n=512,000), and Biobank Japan²⁰ (n=260,000) have also been established. Larger biobanks linking medical records to genotype information are currently being developed, with the All of Us research programme in the USA aiming to recruit over one-million individuals,²¹ and the Our Future Health study in the UK aiming to recruit five million individuals²².

Clinical trials, cohort studies, and case-control studies provide detailed, well characterised phenotypes with precise measurements, making them important for MLTC research, particularly in the case of rare diseases where disease-specific studies are more appropriate. These studies typically include well-defined cases at higher prevalence than found in the general population but often focus on a single disease and rarely target MLTCs. Linking data between single-disease studies presents challenges both from governance and technical perspective. Furthermore, clinical trials often exclude individuals with pre-existing health conditions.

It is important to select a data source that is appropriate for the research question. While biobanks and case-control studies may offer detailed data, they may not be representative of all populations, often over-representing white-European ethnicity, healthier individuals, and those of a higher socioeconomic status²³. Statistical methods are available to adjust for these biases²⁴. Some studies incorporating health questionnaires for self-reported disease ascertainment can be prone to bias. On the other hand, routine healthcare data may enable higher external validity with more population-representative data, but the limitations include disease coding validity and missingness. Certain conditions, such as early-stage chronic kidney disease, may be underestimated if they do not directly affect the patient, while self-reporting can be more reliable than electronic healthcare records for conditions with a higher symptom burden, like pain²⁵.

Data coding

In the UK, health conditions are recorded at various stages of care using different coding systems. For example, Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine Clinical Terms (SNOMED CT) and Read codes have been frequently used in primary care, while International Classification of Diseases (ICD) codes are more common in hospital episode statistics and mortality records. The specificity and validity of these data depend on accurate clinical coding. In the UK, coding quality is incentivised to improve clinical standards. The Quality and Outcomes Framework (QoF) rewards primary care practices based on indicators covering key clinical and public health areas, with 97.5% of practices contributing data²⁶. QoF disease registries improve case identification, as seen with the introduction of the Dementia Identification Scheme in 2015²⁷. However, conditions not included in QoF may remain under-recorded.

The validity of a diagnosis also depends on clinical expertise and the diagnostic tools available. The quality and detail of recorded healthcare variables can vary across data types. Primary care records may include suspected conditions not confirmed by specialists, which can lead to an overestimation of disease prevalence. In contrast, secondary care records, such as hospital episode statistics and mortality records, only capture individuals who are referred or admitted, likely reflecting more severe cases. Therefore, studies need to carefully consider the most appropriate definitions of conditions in terms of sensitivity and specificity, with validation studies being invaluable.

Diagnoses can evolve over time as patients undergo further investigation, and outdated clinical codes may remain in the record even after symptoms resolve or alternative diagnoses are made. Determining whether an individual has multiple concurrent conditions can be challenging, making a life course approach beneficial. Many conditions develop slowly or lead to other conditions later in life, even if they are no longer active. One advantage of electronic health records is the ability to track the sequence in which multiple conditions occur, offering valuable insights into disease progression, though it must be caveated that this sequence is dependent on recording of a disease (potentially due to symptomology) and not disease manifestation itself.

Clinical data on diagnosis, severity, and outcomes can often be incomplete. Diagnoses can be recorded either by clinical codes or as free text, though in order to preserve patient anonymity, the latter is generally unavailable for research. Other problems arise when data are missing non-randomly, potentially reflecting variations in clinical assessment or incomplete records. Some conditions may be more likely to be recorded than others. In primary care, electronic health records are updated by clinicians, and coding depends on their time, so comorbidities unrelated to the consultation's focus may go unrecorded due to time constraints. Conversely, hospital records are entered retrospectively by accredited clinical coders, whose sole role is to ensure accurate coding based on clinicians' notes, however it should be acknowledged that poor notes from clinicians may lead to broad, vague codes being used.

Ensuring consistent phenotypes and interoperability between data sources is crucial, especially as individuals age and accumulate MLTCs²⁸. It can be difficult to map conditions to SNOMED CT, Read, or ICD code since a single condition may map to multiple codes, or multiple conditions can map to the same code. Additionally, codes from different systems do not always correspond directly, even within the UK system. Furthermore, these coding systems are frequently updated, meaning codes may not always map directly to their counterparts in newer versions. For example, ICD-11 was released in 2019 and is gradually being adopted in the healthcare system. To ensure reproducibility, studies on MLTC should provide detailed, transparent lists of the codes used and the rationale behind their selection.

The REporting of studies Conducted using Observational Routinely-collected Data (RECORD) statement offers guidelines for reporting observational studies that use electronic health records²⁹. The Goldacre report³⁰ recommends that large healthcare datasets be held in Trusted Research Environments (TREs) and that data analysis be conducted using Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAPs), with standardised software, analysis plans, and outputs to ensure interoperability and reproducibility. Efforts such as the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model (OMOP CDM) aim to standardise data structure and content of facilitate easier linkage between studies³¹.

Severity

Simply counting long-term conditions does not account for the severity of those conditions. Even when two individuals share the same diagnoses, their outcomes, experiences, costs, and healthcare needs may differ greatly. Severity can be assessed through outcomes such as hospital admissions, specialist consultations, or disease-specific measures like spirometry in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Medication use can also provide insight into disease severity, as treatment guidelines often recommend specific treatments according to severity levels, such as biologic agents for severe asthma.

Patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) are a more patient-focussed way of evaluating severity, though they are often disease-specific and may be difficult to assess in large-scale data-driven research. There could be an opportunity to develop PROMs that are suitable for use in MLTC research, helping to avoid redundancy and better capture patient experiences.

Recommendations for MLTC research

Outputs from two workshops hosted by MLTC Community of Practices highlighted there is no one-size-fits-all approach to MLTC research and analytical decisions will depend on the specific research question being asked. There were however recommendations that all researchers investigating MLTCs should consider:

1. **Tailor the MLTC definition to address the question being asked.** The general definition of MLTCs being an individual with two concurrent conditions is difficult to apply in practice given differences in trait prevalences, severity, data missingness, and difficulties determining which conditions occur at the same time through healthcare records. The choice of what conditions to include will depend on what questions the research is aiming to address, whether this be considering common conditions, MLTCs in particular clinical settings or populations, or investigating specific biological mechanisms.
2. **Use multiple data sources.** Each data source has limitations as discussed above. Performing sensitivity analyses using multiple data sources will ensure results are robust and replicable. This may not always be possible if investigating MLTCs in a particular setting where one data source may be the most appropriate (for example if specifically interested in MLTCs in primary care, then CPRD will likely be the most appropriate source to use). Multiple data sources can also be used to reduce misclassification bias by defining those with a condition as those with that condition from two different data sources.
3. **Consider MLTCs across the life course.** The standard definition of MLTCs is the two conditions must occur concurrently. However, some conditions have long-term impacts after symptoms or treatment have stopped, and some conditions may be present long before they present clinically. Thus, for research purposes it may be important to consider conditions that occur at different time-points.
4. **Standardise data formats.** Difficulties in combining data across studies of different diseases greatly limits the ability to study MLTCs using these resources. New studies should consider standardised data formats, which would greatly improve the ability to harmonise datasets. A set of key covariates to collect in all studies should be developed.
5. **Include all interest-holders in analysis decisions.** Given the complexities of health data systems and number of conditions being studied, including input from individuals with practical experience of inputting data and experience of those personally experiencing MLTCs is vital in understanding the implications of analysis decisions.
6. **Include individuals with MLTCs in studies.** Currently, many studies (particularly clinical trials) exclude individuals with multiple conditions. This not only reduces generalisability of results from the study to the wider population, where MLTCs are common, but also impacts MLTC research itself. There also appears a lack of studies actively recruiting individuals with MLTCs, representing a potential area for future research.
7. **Clearly report analysis decisions.** All analysis decisions will affect the results so clearly stating what choices were made, and the rationale as to why these decisions were chosen, is vital in helping the reader interpret and understand any results. This includes reporting, i) case definition, ii) population studied, iii) data source, iv) disease code-lists or algorithms and coding system (if used), v) date data accessed, vi) limitations of data source including biases in data collection and generalisability to the general population.

Conclusion

With its increasing prevalence, impact on quality of life and complex treatment strategies, MLTCs present growing challenges for healthcare systems. Further tools and resources are needed to aid researchers in designing bespoke disease code lists to address specific research questions. Continued collaboration and knowledge exchange between MLTC researchers, clinicians and patient and public representatives is vital in addressing the challenges identified in this manuscript and maximising impact of future research.

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Author Contributions

RJA, JCD, TMF, PH, IK, GMM, IS, RSMT, AH and JAHM contributed to discussions at the Statistical Methods CoP workshop. RJA, JAHM, LCP, AFS and AMN led the Statistical Methods CoP. JAHM, RJA and SH led the workshop at the Society for Academic Primary Care conference. RJA, AH and JAHM drafted the manuscript with all authors contributing to the final version.

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